

LEGAL ANALYSIS OF THE HARMONIZATION OF LEGAL EDUCATION AND MORAL EDUCATION IN NEW UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: The article studies the theoretical aspects of the harmonization of legal education and moral education in New Uzbekistan, the socio-philosophical and legal analysis of the harmonization of legal education and moral education in New Uzbekistan, the socio-educational tasks and prospects of the harmonization of legal education and moral education in New Uzbekistan. The theoretical and methodological foundations of the harmonization of legal education and moral education in New Uzbekistan are also analyzed.

Key words: education, moral education, dynamics, harmonization, social state, systemic-functional analysis, theoretical-methodological basis, development, legal education, social value, civil society.

Introduction. Law and morality, while closely related, also differ from one another in certain essential features. These differences are as follows. Firstly, legal norms are adopted by the state with the active participation of community organizations and members of society. At the same time, the state has the authority to amend these legal norms, introduce additions to them, and, in some cases, even abolish them altogether. Therefore, in a certain sense, the state is the political foundation of law and its creator. At the same time, law is also a product of the state. Consequently, law does not merely reflect the will of the people but also embodies their will expressed through the supremacy of state interests. In this respect, law should be more accurately defined as a special state mechanism that regulates human behavior. Morality, however, is not created by the state but rather by society as a whole.

Literature review and methods. The issues of harmonizing legal education with moral upbringing, the social aspects of modernizing moral and legal education, in particular, the organization of legal education within this process, the socio-legal status of moral upbringing, and the enhancement of the quality and effectiveness of legal education have been studied in the works of scholars such as A. Veil, D. Easton, J. Dennis, S. Palonsky, J. Piaget, J. Kevin, J. Torney-Purta, R. Bayniyazov, N. Voplenko, O. Demko, Yu. Dmitriev, N. Keyzerov, A. Malko, N. Matuzov, V. Salnikov, L. Matveev, E. Abzalov, N. Vakhobov, D. Dehqonova, Kh. Zakirov, Z. Islamov, I. Kudryavtsev, Z. Madaliev, Kh. Mamatov, O. Nasriddinova, Kh. Odilqoniev, Y. Sadikova, A. Saidov, U. Tojikhonov, N.

Saydalikhodjaeva, R. Turdiboeva, A. Khamraev, Sh. Yakubov, B. Juraev, and S. Juraev.

Results and discussion. The introduction of morality into social life does not require an official authorization or any legal document to legitimize it. What matters most is the approval and acceptance of moral norms by members of society, social groups, and the public at large. In the formation and development of moral norms, the state and other superstructural processes of society also play a significant role. Moreover, both law and morality are historical and cultural values, serving as key criteria that determine the progress of society.

Law differs from other types of social norms, particularly morality, in that legal norms are adopted by the state in agreement with public organizations. While law and the state are inherently interconnected, morality, to a certain degree, maintains only a relative connection with the state.

It should be noted that customs, traditions, and religious teachings also play a positive role in the formation and development of moral and legal norms. Thus, the relationship between law and morality acquires a distinctive dialectical character. Human behavior, regulated on the basis of legal norms, is simultaneously influenced by moral norms. However, unlike legal norms, moral norms do not necessarily require the participation of law in regulating human conduct. From this, it can be concluded that moral norms have a much longer history compared to legal norms. In other words, morality has existed since the very emergence of society, whereas law arose at a certain stage of the evolutionary development of society.

According to the American legal scholar Lawrence Friedman, the concept of law is “as fleeting as a moment, as unstable as a bubble of water, as fragile as porcelain, and yet infinitely multifaceted.” For this reason, when addressing the relationship between law and morality and the place of law within the system of social norms, it becomes essential to gain a deeper understanding of the philosophical essence of law.

The principle of justice is aimed at harmonizing the relations between participants in legal interactions, balancing the relations between the individual and society, and between the citizen and the state. Laws, in turn, reflect this balance on the basis of the principle of justice.

B) The principle of democratization in the formation and implementation of legal norms. The distinctive feature of this principle is that the practical application of legal norms involves the active participation of people’s

representatives, public organizations, non-governmental organizations, labor collectives, political parties, and citizens.

D) The principle of legality. One of the fundamental philosophical essences of law lies in its humanism, that is, its purpose of protecting citizens from unlawful and inhumane encroachments. As an example of implementing this humanitarian principle enshrined in the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan—particularly the state’s commitment to caring for families—one may cite the recently adopted laws in Uzbekistan that provide for the increase of pensions, stipends, and salaries.

The implementation of the above-mentioned principles in practice is directly connected with the core functions of law within the system of social norms. The function of law, in this sense, refers to the realization of its social status within social life. The main criterion determining this social status is the need that arises in the course of social development.

One of the main features that distinguishes legal norms from other social norms is that the state, acting in the interests of the entire population, has the authority to enforce these norms compulsorily and to punish their violation. Naturally, legal institutions and the mass media must explain to citizens the necessity and fairness of state enforcement and of legal responsibility for offenses. At the same time, it is equally important to foster a sense of support for the law as the leading reason for lawful behavior, beyond mere fear of punishment.

Among young people, fear of punishment tends to dominate their attitude toward the law. They often view harsher penalties as the primary means of ensuring compliance with legal norms. From a practical perspective, however, the task lies in helping young people to master the use of all instruments of popular sovereignty and genuine democratic institutions, along with their rights and freedoms, the forms in which they are exercised, and the mechanisms of their protection. These include transparency, the practice of open criticism of mistakes and shortcomings, the opportunity to vote for multiple candidates in elections to self-governing bodies, direct participation in adopting decisions of national importance (such as referenda), the fight against any deviation from the principle of social justice, and the protection of legal order.

Regrettably, the level of legal literacy among adolescents and youth remains very low. Juvenile delinquency is often linked to their unawareness of the legal consequences of defending their rights and lawful interests. According to selective sociological studies, when juveniles serving sentences in correctional

labor colonies were asked, one-third of them admitted that they had been unaware that their actions would entail criminal liability.

In a civil society, enhancing the legal education and moral upbringing of young people is not solely the responsibility of state bodies; it is also an important process requiring the active participation of the public and other non-governmental structures. Ensuring active involvement of youth in non-governmental organizations and consistently raising their level of legal culture is of urgent importance today. Trade unions, youth associations, and women's organizations play a significant role in raising young people's legal awareness and legal culture, and they are entrusted with the task of explaining various forms of legal education and legal upbringing to youth.

In the process of building a civil society, the openness of legal information is crucial, and in this regard the high status of neighborhood (mahalla) institutions must be recognized. Therefore, implementing large-scale measures to improve the legal culture of youth in residential neighborhoods will undoubtedly yield effective results. Broad public awareness campaigns in neighborhoods regarding newly adopted legislation will greatly contribute to raising the level of legal literacy among young people.

It is evident that the development of the legal and moral education of youth is closely interconnected with socio-economic realities. In the process of fostering the legal and moral upbringing of young people within the system of continuous education, several key factors exert a significant influence. These include: the presence within the family of an environment that encourages independent attitudes and critical analysis of the social, legal, and political system of society; the effective organization of the activities of neighborhood (mahalla) institutions in accordance with the social, legal, and political demands of the present time; the ability of educational institutions to properly understand the essence of state policy and approach the legal and political education of the individual on a professional basis within their activities; the role of the mass media in conveying the objectives of the legal and political system to all strata of society without excluding any demographic group; the lawful operation of religious confessions without illegally interfering in state policy; and finally, the ability of every individual to feel a sense of belonging and interest in the social, legal, and political life of society, while independently and consistently cultivating their legal and political culture.

Naturally, the degree of legal and moral activity among young people is never uniform. In some, it may be high; in others, relatively low. Typically, the

level is low among those who possess limited understanding of the functioning of legal institutions and who cannot harmonize their personal interests with those of civil society institutions. By contrast, young people with a higher degree of legal and moral activity display initiative and creativity. For the majority of legally and morally active youth, however, such activity tends to take the form of execution and implementation. Both manifestations of youth legal and moral activity—whether creative or executory—hold practical as well as theoretical significance.

The legal and moral activity of youth is not carried out solely on an individual basis; rather, it takes shape through collective association founded on shared goals and interests. Such associations may take diverse forms, and youth activity may be expressed both individually and collectively. From this it follows that political institutions play a crucial role in developing the legal and moral education of young people.

The inclination toward legal and moral engagement is not equally strong among all youth. This is because the concept of legal and moral upbringing itself is more subjective than universal in nature. From this perspective, youth engagement in legal and moral activity proceeds in harmony with their psychology, physical and biological characteristics, heredity, and individual preferences and desires. In our view, while it is important not to dismiss various measures aimed at fostering youth engagement, greater effectiveness can be achieved by leveraging the very qualities inherent in young people themselves. In particular, campaigns and advocacy initiatives conducted by legally and politically active and leadership-oriented youth are bound to prove more effective. Therefore, there is a need to promote the “youth wings” of emerging political parties within our political system as well as various youth clubs.

As Aristotle rightly defined: *“Man is a political being, and at the same time a social being inclined toward community. His ability to satisfy the multifaceted demands of normal life and to attain happiness is realized through his relationship with others.”* Indeed, as a political being, an individual’s guarantee of achieving specific political goals and interests lies in uniting within associations, movements, and groups. This holds particular significance in the participation of youth in political processes.

Conclusion

In order to harmonize the legal and moral education of youth, it is first necessary to acquire sufficient legal and moral knowledge. Within the process of educating and nurturing young people, particular attention is given to the

provision of moral knowledge and upbringing alongside formal education. Specifically, the inclusion of socio-political disciplines such as History, Society and the Individual, Applied Geography, Jurisprudence, Fundamentals of Spirituality, Aesthetics, Family Psychology, the Fundamental Concepts and Principles of the National Independence Ideology, the Constitution of Uzbekistan, and Fundamentals of Economics—regardless of specialization—across all educational institutions, plays an essential role. Furthermore, the regular organization of extracurricular rituals and events of both educational and political significance contributes significantly to the development of political knowledge and skills among youth.

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